

Synthesis of Nanocatalyst for Environmental Remediation

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OBJECTIVES

- Synthesis of visible light active photocatalyst
- Physico-chemical characterization of materials
- photocatalyst employing XRD, SEM-EDAX, HR-TEM, FT-IR, DRS-UV and BET
- Degradation of endocrine disrupting chemicals using visible light active photocatalyst
- Degradation in slurry batch and continuous flow reactors

SYNTHESIS MESOPOROUS Fe₂O₃-TiO₂

- The following materials used for synthesis
- Pluronic P123, Titanium(IV) isopropoxide, Iron nitrate nanahydrate, Ethanol
- Pluronic P123 act as structure directing agent
- Titanium(IV) isopropoxide, Iron nitrate hexahydrate metal sources for Ti and Fe
- Prepared by Sol-gel method

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

XRD

- Characteristic reflection of Fe₂O₃ and TiO₂
- Isomorphous substitution of iron in TiO₂ or titanium in Fe₂O₃ was evident
- The crystal size was in the range of 16 to 19 nm

N₂ SORPTION STUDY

Catalyst Fe:Ti ratio	Specific surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	Pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	Pore diameter (nm)
3:1	102.85	0.363	9.15
1:1	106.37	0.364	8.81
1:3	109.54	0.361	8.68

DRS – UV SPECTRA

- Their band gap excitation in the DRS-UV spectrum showed a broad absorption band due to overlap of TiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ absorbance

FT-IR SPECTRA

- FT-IR spectra of calcined sample showed the characteristic peaks for the absorbed water (3200 – 3500 cm⁻¹) and OH bending vibration at 1600 cm⁻¹
- Below 700 cm⁻¹ showed metal – oxygen bending vibration

SEM IMAGES

- The SEM images of Fe₂O₃-TiO₂ revealed particles are agglomerated each other

PHOTOCATALYTIC ACTIVITY

Evaluation of Photocatalytic Activity of Fe₂O₃-TiO₂

- Methylene blue as modern pollutant for photodegradation study
- Methylene blue were performed in aqueous medium in a slurry batch reactor
- Irradiated with solar light
- Aliquots were withdrawn at specific time intervals
- The extent of mineralization of Methylene blue were studied by using a total organic carbon analyzer
- The percent of organic carbon decreased with increase of irradiation time

Methylene Blue degradation

CONCLUSIONS

- The present work focuses on the photocatalytic activity of coupled Fe₂O₃-TiO₂ nanomaterials using solar light
- The degradation of Methylene blue were rapid in the presence of the catalyst and light compared to light alone
- Based on the results of this study it is established that this catalyst can be applied for the degradation of other organic pollutants in water

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